

Ecological infrastructures outside greenhouses – impact on Hymenoptera Parasitica abundance and diversity

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Abstract: Plant ecological infrastructures are important for the success of biological control, providing pollen, nectar, alternative prey and hosts for parasitoids and predators, as well as shelter. Within the PRIMA ASTER project, a two-year study was carried out in 2023-2024 to assess the abundance and diversity of the Hymenoptera Parasitica in the surrounding of two greenhouses used for tomato production in a farm, in the Oeste region, Portugal. In the first year, four seasonal samplings were conducted, one in the end of spring, two in the summer, and one in autumn, using four Malaise traps outside each greenhouse. Samplings were repeated in the second year, after installing a strip of selected plants with different flowering periods and strata (herbs and shrubs) outside one of the greenhouses, as ecological infrastructures (*Foeniculum vulgare*, *Coriandrum sativum*, *Rosmarinus prostratus*, *Borago officinalis*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Thymus vulgaris*, *Phacelia tanacetifolia*, *Helichrysum italicum*, *Lavandula stoechas*, and *Lobularia maritima*). Data is being analysed, aimed at assessing the seasonal dynamics of wasp captures, as well as the diversity of hymenopteran families and their relative importance. The potential effect of the installed ecological infrastructure will be also evaluated.

Key words: Parasitoids, protected crops, tomato, biological control

Extended summary: Plant ecological infrastructures are important for the success of biological control, providing pollen, nectar, alternative prey and hosts for parasitoids and predators, as well as shelter (Arnó et al., 2018; Boller et al., 2004; Franco et al., 2006). Within the PRIMA ASTER project, a two-year study was carried out in 2023 and 2024 to assess the abundance and diversity of the Hymenoptera Parasitica in the surrounding of two greenhouses used for tomato production in a farm, in Silveira, Torres Vedras (Oeste region, Portugal). In the first year, four seasonal samplings were conducted, one in the end of spring, two in the summer and one in autumn, using four Malaise traps outside each greenhouse. A strip of selected plants with different flowering periods and strata (herbs and shrubs) was installed in late winter outside one of the greenhouses as ecological infrastructures. This strip consisted of fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*), rosemary (*Rosmarinus prostratus*), borage (*Borago officinalis*), laurustine (*Viburnum tinus*), common heather (*Calluna vulgaris*), thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), fiddleneck or lacy phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*), curry plant or Italian strawflower

(*Helichrysum italicum*), Spanish lavender (*Lavandula stoechas*), and sweet alyssum (*Lobularia maritima*). Sampling was repeated in 2024 outside both greenhouses. A total of 1418 and 1646 wasps were captured in 2023 and 2024, respectively, distributed among 20 families, dominated by Ichneumonidae and Braconidae, which represent about 88 % of the captures: Ichneumonidae (49.1 %), Braconidae (38.7 %), Eulophidae (3.4 %), Figitidae (3.1 %), Pteromalidae (1.3 %), Dryinidae (1.1 %), Diapriidae (0.7 %), Megaspilidae (0.6 %), Chalcididae (0.5 %), Encyrtidae (0.5 %), Proctotrupidae (0.3 %), Eurytomidae (0.2 %), Perilampidae (0.2 %), Mymaridae (0.1 %), Evaniidae (0.1 %), Scelionidae (0.1 %), Bethylinidae (0.1 %), Torymidae (0.1 %), Ceraphronidae (< 0.1 %), and Gasteruptiidae (< 0.1 %). In both years, captures were maximal in spring, followed by summer and autumn. In 2024, the mean number of wasp captures obtained in the traps surrounding the greenhouse where the ecological infrastructure was installed registered 30 % increase in relation to 2023, whereas those surrounding the control greenhouse only registered 2 %. The increase was maximal in spring, just after the set up flowering strip. Braconidae was the family registering the highest increase in 2024 (47 %), compared to Ichneumonidae (7 %). Preliminary results suggest a positive effect of the installed flowering strip in enhancing the abundance of Hymenoptera Parasitica in the surrounding area of tomato greenhouses.

References

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